

Article

COVID-19 and its Challenges in Education, Business and Technology

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Abstract

Besides its worrying effects on human life, the novel strain of coronavirus has the potential to significantly slow down the global economy. Several industries have been adversely impacted due to the spread of COVID-19. It is evident that the global economy is grinding to a halt. As business close to help prevent transmission of COVID-19, financial concerns and job losses are one of the first human impacts of the virus. We have seen the significant economic impact of the coronavirus on financial markets and vulnerable industries such as manufacturing, tourism, hospitality and travel. Travel and tourism account for 10 % of the global GDP and 50 million jobs are at risk worldwide. Global tourism, travel and hospitality companies closing down affects SMEs globally. Responding to the crisis requires global cooperation among governments, international organisations and the business community, which is at the centre of the World Economic Forum's mission as the International Organization for Public-Private Cooperation. The pandemic is also expected to have a huge impact on global education. According to UNESCO monitoring, over 100 countries have implemented nationwide closures, impacting nearly 90 % of the world's student population. School closures impact not only students, teachers and families, but have far reaching economic and societal consequences. School closures in response to COVID-19 have shed light on various social and economic issues, including student debt, digital learning, food insecurity, and homelessness, as well as access to child care, health care, housing, internet and disability services. Efforts to stem the spread of COVID-19 through non-pharmaceutical interventions and preventive measures such as social-distancing and self-isolation have prompted the widespread closure of schooling in over 100 countries.

Keywords: COVID-19, challenges, business, education, technology

Introduction

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-COV-2). The disease was first identified in 2019 in Wuhan, the capital of China's Hubei province, and has since spread globally, resulting in the 2019-2020 coronavirus pandemic. Common symptoms include fever, cough, and shortness of breath. Other symptoms may include muscle pain, sputum production, diarrhoea, sore throat, abdominal pain, and loss of smell or taste. While the majority of cases result in mild symptoms, some progress to pneumonia and multi-organ failure. As of March 25, 2020, the overall rate of deaths per number of diagnosed cases is 4.5 percent; ranging from 0.2 percent to 15 percent according to age group and other health problems. The virus is mainly spread during close contact and via respiratory droplets produced when people cough or sneeze. Respiratory droplets may be produced during breathing but the virus is not considered airborne. People may also catch COVID-19 by touching a contaminated surface and then their face. It is more contagious when people are symptomatic, although spread may be possible before symptoms appear. The virus can live on surfaces up to 72 hours. Time from exposure to onset of symptoms is generally between two and fourteen days, with an average of five days. The standard method of diagnosis is by five days. The standard method of diagnosis is by reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (rRT-PCR) from a nasopharyngeal swab. The infection can also be diagnosed from a combination of symptoms, risk factors and a chest CT scan showing features of pneumonia.

Recommended measures to prevent infection include frequent hand washing, social distancing (maintaining physical distance from others, especially from those with symptoms), covering coughs and sneezes with a tissue or inner elbow, and keeping unwashed hands away from the face. The use of masks is recommended by some national health authorities for those who suspect they have the virus and their caregivers, but not for the general public, although simple cloth masks may be used by those who desire them. There is no vaccine or specific antiviral treatment for COVID-19.

Management involves treatment of symptoms, supportive care, isolation and experimental measures. The World Health Organisation (WHO) declared the 2019-2020 coronavirus outbreak a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) on 30 January 2020 and a pandemic on 11 March 2020. Local transmission of the disease has been recorded in many countries across all six WHO regions.

Most people infected with the COVID-19 virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment. Older people, and those with underlying medical problems like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, chronic respiratory disease and cancer are more likely to develop serious illness.

The best way to prevent and slow down transmission is to be well informed about the COVID-19 virus, the disease it causes and how it spreads. Protect yourself and others from infection by washing your hands or using an alcohol based rub frequently and not touching your face.

The COVID-19 virus spreads primarily through droplets of saliva or discharge from the nose when an infected person coughs or sneezes, so it's important that you also practice respiratory etiquette (for example, by coughing into a flexed elbow).

At this time, there are no specific vaccines or treatments for COVID-19. However, there are many ongoing clinical trials evaluating potential treatments. WHO will continue to provide updated information as soon as clinical findings become available.

COVID-19 is thought to have originated in a seafood market where wildlife was sold illegally. On February 7, 2020, Chinese researchers said the virus could have spread from an infected animal to humans through illegally trafficked pangolins, prized in Asia for food and medicine. Scientists have pointed to either bats or snakes as possible sources.

Impacts of COVID-19 on Global Education

Over a billion students worldwide are unable to go to school or university, due to measures to stop the spread

of COVID-19. The pandemic is expected to have a huge impact on global education.

According to UNESCO monitoring, over 100 countries have implemented nationwide closures, impacting nearly 90 % of the world's student population. School closures impact not only students, teachers and families, but have far reaching economic and societal consequences. School closures in response to COVID-19 have shed light on various social and economic issues, including student debt, digital learning, food insecurity, and homelessness, as well as access to child care, health care, housing, internet and disability services.

Efforts to stem the spread of COVID-19 through non-pharmaceutical interventions and preventive measures such as social-distancing and self-isolation have prompted the widespread closure of primary, secondary, and tertiary schooling in over 100 countries.

Impacts of COVID-19 on Global Business

Besides its worrying effects on human life, the novel strain of coronavirus has the potential to significantly slow down the global economy. Several industries have been adversely impacted due to the spread of COVID-19 globally. It is evident that the global economy is grinding to a halt. As business close to help prevent transmission of COVID-19, financial concerns and job losses are one of the first human impacts of the virus.

We have seen the significant economic impact of the coronavirus on financial markets and vulnerable industries such as manufacturing, tourism, hospitality and travel. Travel and tourism account for 10 % of the global GDP and 50 million jobs are at risk worldwide. Global tourism, travel and hospitality companies closing down affects SMEs globally.

Responding to the crisis requires global cooperation among governments, international organisations and the business community, which is at the centre of the World Economic Forum's mission as the International Organization for Public-Private Cooperation.

The Forum has created the COVID Action Platform, a global platform to convene the business community for collective action, protect people's livelihoods and facilitate business continuity, and mobilize support for the COVID-19 response. The platform is created with the support of the World Health Organisation and is open to all businesses and industry groups, as well as other stakeholders, aiming to integrate and inform joint action. As an organisation, the Forum has a track record of supporting efforts to contain epidemics.

Impacts of COVID-19 on Global Technology: Online Education and Challenges faced by Teachers in a Rural School during COVID – 19 pandemic

Conducting online class in a rural area is a big challenge faced by the teachers because of the digital divide, access to devices, many parents are not being educated and even network problems. There is a good response from parents and students. Some students have formed home study groups where they share their devices. Also the teachers are facing a lot of problems while taking online classes in rural areas due to poor network connection. Students in rural areas are facing a lot of problems due to poverty, illiterate parents, poor data connectivity, lack of access to laptops and smartphones, power issues and so on. COVID – 19 pandemic has created a worse situation in many countries. The Government of India has recommended moving to online learning as an arrangement to evade any disruptions in academic calendars. But when it comes to online education, rural population is not completely equipped with utilities like fast internet, uninterrupted power supply and electronic devices. Some of the major challenges of online education in rural areas are like lack of digital literacy and infrastructural support, limited availability of technological devices, lack of familiarity with digital technology, shortage of teachers and so on.

Online Education is a kind of education which is taken through electronic media like Television, Mobile Phone, Laptop, Desktop, PC Tablet, and so on. Online Class is taken with the help of the electronic devices. Online Classes can be taken easily by sitting at our home itself. Today in this age of globalisation, the means of communication has become very faster. As a result of Globalisation, the means of communication has become very faster in this age of Science and

Technology. As a result of the advancement of science and technology, now we are able to take online classes using various kinds of electronic devices. The online education includes different types of teachings like webinar, classes, meetings, etc. We can use different types of social media like Zoom Cloud Meetings, Facebook, WhatsApp, Google Meet, and so on. Now a days during the time of COVID-19 pandemic, the online education has become very important. The government has also opened different Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) to provide online education to students. So, online education has become very important during the time of the COVID - 19 pandemic. Online Education are of great importance now-a-days as we can take it easily by sitting at our home itself or from any location. We can have online education by taking and smart devices like smartphone, PC tablet, laptop, desktop, etc. We can access to online education easily just by using our devices anywhere. Online Education has a great significance now-a-days. Since education has a great significance, so online education is very important in this time of COVID-19 pandemic. As a result of online class we can continue our education even during lockdown. We can listen to the teachers even without going to the school and classroom. It is one of the cheapest means of taking classes. We can learn from our home itself without going out. It has become more important and popular during the time of COVID - 19 pandemic.

With the help of online education, we can take valuable and online classes including webinars, online workshops, conferences, meetings and so on. Online Education has become very important and popular means of communication. Today internet has become very useful. We can do many things with the help of internet. In this age of 21st century the world has totally changed. With the help of internet we can do a lot of useful works. Internet has also become very useful in educational sector. At present, with the help of internet, we can take online class, online conference, online examination, online seminar, webinars etc. Now a days, Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) has been introduced in many schools, colleges and university. It has helped the students a lot. Infact we can learn many things by sitting at our home itself with the help of internet. Internet has helped us a lot in this age of science and technology. Today with

the help of internet, we can do many things like playing games, watching video, listening to music, reading books, magazines, newspapers, etc. It has become very popular among the young generation. We can do many things by sitting at our home itself like earning money, online shopping, online buying and selling of products, business, teaching and learning, etc. We get a lot of information by accessing to the internet. One can learn about the different events going on in the world simply by accessing to the internet. Today each and every part of the globe is well connected with the help of internet. Earlier if we want to reach America, we have to cross seven continents and five oceans. But today we can reach it within 24 hours. We can connect to people in any part of the world in no time. We can use different social medias like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, etc. It has made our means of communication very fast. Today it has become very popular among people specially the young generation. During the time of COVID – 19 pandemic also, today we are well connected with the help of Internet. As a result of lockdown due to the Global Coronavirus pandemic, people cannot come out from their homes. But still we are well connected with the help of Internet. So we cannot ignore the uses of Internet in this age of 21st century. Let Internet be used for the development of the society.

Conclusion

Coronavirus disease 2019 or COVID - 19 is an infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2(also known as SARS-COV-2). The disease was first identified in 2019 in Wuhan, the capital city of China's Hubei province, and has since spread globally, resulting in the 2019-2020 coronavirus or COVID – 19 pandemic. Common symptoms include fever, cough, and shortness of breath. Other symptoms may include muscle pain, sputum production, diarrhoea, sore throat, abdominal pain, and loss of smell or taste. While the majority of cases result in mild symptoms, some progress to pneumonia and multi-organ failure. As of March 25, 2020, the overall rate of deaths per number of diagnosed cases is 4.5 percent; ranging from 0.2 percent to 15 percent according to age group and other health problems. The virus is mainly spread during close contact and via respiratory droplets produced when people cough or sneeze. Respiratory droplets

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